

Separation of Germanium from Arsenic by Paper Chromatography

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LEDERER¹ was able to separate germanium from Arsenic and other elements by paper chromatography using *n*-butanol saturated with N HCl using the ascending technique. The R_f values were Ge(IV), 0.26; As(V), 0.84; and As(III) 0.52. Ladenbauer and Hecht² made use of alcohols mixed with HNO₃ as solvents in the paper chromatographic separation of germanium by the descending technique.

In this communication we report our studies on the paper chromatographic separation of these two elements using ketones and ether solvent systems. Each solvent was studied in the three acid media—hydrochloric, hydrobromic and nitric acid.

Experimental

The descending technique was employed for the separations. Whatman No. 1 'Chromatographic quality' filter paper was used as the inert support. The strips were of the size 8 × 45 cm.

Chemicals and Reagents

Germanium dioxide sample was of the purest quality supplied by Fairmount Chemical Company, New York. The arsenious oxide and sodium arsenate were 'pro analyse' grade samples supplied by E. Merck.

The germanium solution (0.06%) was prepared by weighing the requisite quantity of germanium dioxide and mixing with 0.5 gm. of sodium carbonate and 25 ml of water. The sodium germanate thus obtained was neutralised with sufficient hydrochloric acid and diluted to 100 ml.

1% solutions of As(III) and As(V) were similarly prepared.

A 0.05% solution of phenyl fluorone in a mixture of ethyl alcohol and dilute sulphuric acid (75 : 25) was used as a spraying reagent for the identification of Ge(IV).

The yellow spot obtained when the paper strip was exposed to hydrogen sulphide identified As(III).

As(V) was identified by the benzidine-potassium iodide reagent spray which is prepared as follows : 0.1 gm. of benzidine and 0.1 gm. of potassium iodide were dissolved in 10 ml of 3 N HCl and the solution was filtered. The solution when sprayed identified the As(V) as a dark brown spot.

The solvents acetone, methyl ethyl ketone (MEK), methyl isobutyl ketone (MIBK) were of laboratory

reagent quality and purified freshly before use according to the standard procedures.

Results

The following Table summarises the R_f values with solvent systems of varying compositions :

Sl. No	Solvent system (vol. %)		R_f values			
			Ge (IV)	As (III)	As (V)	
1.	Acetone	(90%) + HCl	(10%)	0.95	0.72	0.85
2.	Acetone	(90%) + HNO ₃	(10%)	0.80	0.12	0.65
3.	Acetone	(90%) + HBr	(10%)	0.68	0.50	0.86
4.	MEK	(90%) + HCl	(10%)	0.82	0.81	0.69
5.	MEK	(90%) + HNO ₃	(10%)	0.16	0.12	0.42
6.	MEK	(90%) + HBr	(10%)	0.28	0.35	0.50
7.	MIBK	(90%) + HCl	(10%)	0.59	0.48	0.11
8.	MIBK*	(90%) + HNO ₃	(10%)	0.10	0.10	0.13
9.	MIBK*	(90%) + HBr	(10%)	0.48	0.43	0.40
10.	Dioxane	(90%) + HCl	(10%)	0.74	0.70	0.91
11.	Dioxane	(90%) + HNO ₃	(10%)	0.40	0.83	0.73
12.	Dioxane	(90%) + HBr	(10%)	0.11	0.10	0

* Two layers formed and the upper layer was taken.

It can be seen that in all the cases the R_f values for Ge(IV) and As(III) are close, while the values for Ge(IV) and As(V) are wide enough to be amenable for separation. As(III) was therefore converted to As(V) by the addition of small quantities of hydrogen peroxide before running the chromatogram. This pretreatment gave very satisfactory separation of the two elements with the solvent systems 2, 5, 7, 10 and 11. Further, the separation time is of the order of 6-8 hours as compared to 22-24 hours with butanol-HCl/HNO₃ systems recommended by Lederer and Ladenbauer.

References

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β -Resorcyaldehyde as a Reagent for the Spectrophotometric Determination of Ferric Ions

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WHILE a number of phenolic carbonyl compounds have been investigated as reagents for the spectrophotometric determination of ferric ions, β -resorcyaldehyde has not been investigated so far for this purpose. The present article reports the use of β -resorcyaldehyde as reagent for the spectrophotometric determination of ferric ions.

Experimental

β -Resorcyaldehyde : 0.005 M solution was prepared in 40% ethyl alcohol.